

Optimized T1 and T2 Weighted Structural Imaging on Clinical 7 Tesla Systems Employing Single Channel Universal Pulses

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Categories

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Synopsis

We present single channel universal pulses for optimized T1 and T2 weighted (fluid suppressed) imaging on clinical ultra high-field systems. B0 and B1 inhomogeneities are effectively mitigated, and no pulse calculations are necessary during the imaging session. Compared to a parallel transmission set-up, SAR estimation is less complex and there is no potential risk of producing a “hot-spot”, making this approach a promising tool for clinical applications such as lesion detection.

Summary of Main Findings

Single channel universal pulses for T1 and T2 weighted imaging are designed and tested in vivo at clinical 7T systems for improved image quality.

Introduction

In the last years, ultra high-field (7T) imaging has become an increasingly important modality for neuroscience applications. However, various issues compromise image quality and scanning efficiency at UHF: B1 and B0 inhomogeneities induce signal drop outs and/or insufficient suppression of unwanted tissue components, and SAR limitations reduce scanning efficiency. The use of parallel transmission (pTX) mitigates these issues efficiently, and by applying universal pulses, calibration scans and online pulse calculations are rendered unnecessary [1]. So far, pTX is limited to research settings and is not yet applicable for clinical use. To overcome this limitation we propose single channel universal pulses (sTX-UPs, [2]) for clinical ultra high field applications. We developed and implemented non-selective excitation, inversion, as well as refocusing pulses to facilitate the acquisition of all standard image contrasts for structural imaging (T1w, T2w, T2w-FLAIR).

Methods

Single channel universal pulses were calculated to enable uniform excitation, refocusing, and inversion patterns over the whole brain by utilizing the GRAPE algorithm [3, 4] and minimizing the NMRSE of the flip angle. The optimization was initialized with SPINS pulses [5]. All pulses were designed under explicit power constraints and with simultaneous optimization of the k-space trajectory under slew rate constraints. The optimization was based on B0 and B1+ data derived from a population

of healthy adults in a pre-study, rendering RF calibration procedures unnecessary during the actual imaging session.

For T1w (MPRAGE) contrast an excitation pulse (small tip angle approximation, nominal FA=5deg), and an inversion pulse (high flip angle regime, nominal FA=180deg) was calculated.

For T2w (SPACE) contrast a scalable RF pulse [5] with nominal flip angle of 90deg was calculated. The pulse was used for both excitation, and refocusing within the variable flip angle train. The excitation pulse phase was shifted by 90deg relative to the refocusing pulses to fulfill the CPMG condition. For fluid suppression a universal pulse T2prep module was used [6]. All refocusing pulses were implemented using a symmetric RF shape and k-space trajectory to fulfill the CPMG condition. This was achieved by concatenating two excitation pulses (Figure 1).

Imaging experiments were performed on a MAGNETOM 7TPlus and a FDA approved (CE labeled) 7T Terra scanner (Siemens AG, Healthcare Sector, Erlangen, Germany) using standard head array coils with one transmit and 32 receive channels (Nova Medical, Wilmington, USA). For pulse performance analysis and comparison to a parallel transmission set-up, additional experiments were performed with 8 transmit channels.

Imaging was performed in two healthy volunteers. Imaging parameters: 0.8x0.8x0.8mm resolution, matrix size 320x320x208 (whole brain coverage). MPRAGE: TR/TI = 2500/1100ms, total scan time 4:45 min. FLAIR sequence parameters: TR = 9000ms, TI/TE = 2100/300ms, total scan time 5:09 min.

Results

Figure 2 shows a Bloch simulation for the 90deg SPACE refocusing pulse. The flip angle homogeneity of the sTX-UP is similar to the pTX-UP, however at the cost of a longer pulse duration (2.7ms vs. 0.76ms) due to the loss of the coil channels degree of freedom. Furthermore, a slight SNR and CNR penalty can be observed, as non-optimized standard protocols have been used so far for all acquisitions. Figures 3+4 show MPRAGE and FLAIR images acquired with CP-mode, sTX-UP, and pTX-UP pulses. Due to the B1 insensitivity of universal pulses, no artifacts originating from incomplete inversion/refocusing are visible and B1 inhomogeneities are effectively mitigated. As can be seen in Fig. 3+4 (bottom right) even down to the cerebellum high signal level, as well as effective inversion can be maintained and the images appear significantly more homogeneous over the brain compared to CP-mode. Figure 5 shows the same imaging protocols acquired on clinical 7T systems. Due to the longer pulse durations of the sTX-UPs

Discussion/Conclusion

Substantial improvement of image excitation, refocusing, and inversion homogeneity over the whole brain was achieved utilizing sTX-UPs. So far, only preliminary data has been acquired, using standard imaging protocols. Future work will include optimization of the imaging protocols with regard to SNR/CNR, in order to account for the longer pulse durations of the sTX-UP pulses. Additionally, the pulse performance will be further optimized by adapting pulse duration and energy to the updated protocol needs.

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Figure 1: 180deg refocusing pulse of the T2prep module. The pulse is created by concatenating two 90deg excitation pulses. The pulse symmetry is needed to achieve phase coherence over the whole brain volume between excitation and refocusing. The first half of the pulse is used for excitation (by adding a constant 90deg phase shift). Hence, it is guaranteed that the phase profiles of excitation and refocusing are identical.

Figure 2: Bloch simulation for the SPACE excitation pulse. *Left:* Standard rectangular CP-mode excitation. *Middle:* pTX-UP excitation. *Right:* sTX-UP excitation. Both, sTX-UP and pTX-UP achieve a homogeneous flip angle over the whole brain volume. However, for the sTX-UP at cost of a long pulse duration due to the loss of the channel degree of freedom compared to the pTX-UP.

Figure 3: Comparison of MPRAGE imaging protocols: *Left:* Standard adiabatic inversion and rectangular CP-mode excitation. *Middle:* pTX-UPs for both, inversion and excitation. *Right:* sTX-UP application for excitation and inversion. In comparison to the CP mode acquisition, B0 and B1 inhomogeneities are mitigated for the universal pulse acquisition.

Figure 4: Comparison of FLAIR imaging protocols: *Left* Standard CP-mode protocol: Signal drop-outs in the Cerebellum. *Middle, Right:* The universal pulses generate an homogeneous FLAIR contrast over the field of view. Even down to the cerebellum full inversion is maintained. The sTX-UP achieves as slightly better homogeneity, but less SNR due to the longer refocusing pulses.

Figure 5: Universal pulse acquisition on clinical systems: *Left* (standard protocol): Signal loss. *Middle, Right:* The universal pulses generate an homogeneous FLAIR contrast over the field of view. Even down to the cerebellum full inversion is maintained. The sTX-UP has slightly better homogeneity, but less SNR due to the longer RF pulses.